

1 **Shank3 activation in the blood in humans with Autism.**

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7 Gene expression signatures for a given disease are likely most authentic in the tissue of origin or tissue of
8 interest. Hematopoietic signatures for chronic disease are accepted in blood-based autoimmune disease
9 but the representation of the disease signature in the peripheral blood for diseases of the CNS remains
10 incompletely understood. Here we measured total transcription in the blood by microarray in humans with
11 Autism. We report activation of *Shank3* in the peripheral blood in humans with Autism as a key,
12 component gene product of the autism spectrum disorder (ASD) gene signature. Components of the
13 disease signature may be represented at physiologically relevant levels in the blood, enabling capture of
14 the disease transcriptome landscape even when originating or affecting the CNS.

15 Citations

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